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Digital Technologies for Managing Natural Disasters

Bridging the Gap Between Potential and Reality

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Inside the FGVin

FGVin is the Innovation Center of FGV-EAESP. We are a research center focused on innovation across different sectors, aiming to build a strong network that fosters knowledge exchange and creation.

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More than academic research, we seek to apply insights to solve complex challenges in the Brazilian context from a global perspective.

Our center is composed of researchers from diverse and interdisciplinary fields, all deeply committed to advancing innovation.

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About digital technologies

What is the degree of use of digital technologies by humanitarian support networks in the United States and the United Kingdom to manage natural disasters?

Despite its potential, why is the degree of utilization still low?

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Natural disasters

Disasters are events that disrupt the normal functioning of systems. Some natural disasters occur suddenly, such as earthquakes, cyclones, and hurricanes, while others develop gradually. Although they are called natural, many of these events are worsened by human actions on the environment. Nowadays, natural disasters are becoming increasingly common and affect millions of people over the years. Therefore, a fast and efficient response from humanitarian support networks is essential to save lives.

Recent natural disasters

- o Flooding in Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil (182 deaths and around 600,000 displaced) – 2024
- o Flooding in Valencia, Spain (over 220 deaths) – 2024
- o Flooding in Texas, United States (at least 52 deaths) – 2025
- o Wildfires in Southern California, United States – 2025 (At least 30 deaths, and over 200,000 people evacuated)

Credit: Pixabay (<https://pixabay.com/>)

Digital technologies for disaster management

Digital technologies, which connect the real world to the virtual one, are fundamental for supply chain management as they enhance visibility, collaboration, flexibility, and agility in decision-making. In humanitarian support networks focused on prevention, monitoring, alleviating suffering, and minimizing damage after a disaster, these technologies are also extremely valuable. Events can be anticipated through IoT sensors; drones can be used for area mapping; and virtual reality technologies enable the planning and training of actions before they take place.

In this regard, the present working paper aims to present the degree of utilization of the main digital technologies used for disaster management:

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- Machine Learning
- Blockchain
- Virtual Reality
- Internet of Things
- 3D Printing
- Robotic
- AI

Responses of participants

To assess the degree of utilization of these technologies, an online questionnaire was conducted, yielding 225 valid responses, most of which were from managers of large companies (more than 1,000 employees). Of these, 165 respondents were professionals from companies in the United States, and 60 from companies in the United Kingdom. Regarding the type of organization, the majority belonged to the healthcare sector (72 respondents).

Degree of technology use

The chart below illustrates the degree of utilization of digital technologies. It is evident that, across all technologies, usage rates are higher in the United States compared to the United Kingdom. On average, considering both groups, the most widely used technology for managing natural disasters was Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (2.92), followed by the use of Drones (2.73). Conversely, Drone Swarms (1.78) and 3D Printing were the least adopted technologies among the humanitarian networks surveyed.

Why do these humanitarian networks make only limited use of digital technologies?

Given the limited use of these technologies, we also sought to identify the main barriers to their adoption. The findings are presented in the following chart.

Barriers

The **three barriers** that have the **greatest impact** on technology use, according to the overall average, are:

- High cost (4.87)
- Lack of resources to invest in technology (4.30)
- Lack of knowledge about available technological solutions (4.21)

The **three barriers** that have the least **impact on technology use**, according to the overall average, are:

- Lack of pressure from other organizations (3.31)
- Lack of transparency in the use of resources (3.35)
- Limited involvement of end users (3.36)

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